

REACTIONS OF HYPONITRITES. PART III. ESTIMATION OF NITRITE IN PRESENCE OF HYPONITRITE

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Two important observations which permit of estimation of nitrite in presence of hyponitrite have been made, viz., (i) thiourea-acetic acid has little action on hyponitrites and (ii) in solution or suspension, hyponitrites are completely decomposed on heating in a boiling water-bath.

No attempts appear to have been made in the past to estimate nitrite in presence of hyponitrites. As nitrite and nitrate are produced in the thermal decomposition of hyponitrites, estimation of these in the presence of each other has practical utility quite apart from the value of such methods in analytical chemistry.

Thiourea-acetic acid is a well known reagent for the estimation of nitrite and nitrate. The action of this reagent on hyponitrites does not appear to have been studied before. The present authors have studied the action of this reagent on (i) sodium hyponitrite (soluble) and (ii) calcium hyponitrite (insoluble) and found that it has little or no action on the substances and nitrite can therefore be accurately estimated in presence of hyponitrites. As sodium hyponitrite has some action, the aqueous solution containing it, must be boiled before being put into the nitrometer. Boiling is found to destroy the hyponitrite. The action of water on hyponitrites was studied by Partington and Shah (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 2071; 1932, 2589) at room temperature and they found that the sodium salt was incompletely decomposed in two days, while the calcium salt remained unaffected. The present authors repeated these observations to ascertain if the hyponitrites could be quickly decomposed by boiling with water. As no nitrite or nitrate is produced in the reaction, accurate estimation of the contained nitrite can be had if the hyponitrite underwent complete decomposition. This is found to be the case.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sodium hyponitrite and calcium hyponitrite were prepared according to Partington and Shah (*loc. cit.*). These were analysed for purity.

Sodium Hyponitrite: (i) 1.9082 g. hydrated substance left 1.0322 g. anhydrous salt, giving 92.85 g. *i.e.*, about 5H₂O per g. mol. of anhydrous salt.

(ii) 0.0119 g. anhydrous substance gave 0.0130 g. NaCl, while 0.0447 g. anhydrous substance gave 0.1194 g. AgCl. (Found: Na, 43.1; N₂O₂, 55.9. Calc. for Na₂N₂O₂: Na, 43.4; N₂O₂, 56.6 per cent).

(iii) 0.014 g. of the substance required 5.85 c.c. of 0.04493 N-KCNS working as 0.01384 g. Na₂N₂O₂.

Calcium Hyponitrite: (i) 0.0242 g. gave 0.0192 g. CaSO_4 .

(ii) 0.0514 g. gave 6.6 c.c. N_2 (N. T. P.) in Dumas estimation. (Found: Ca, 0.00564 g. i. e., Ca, 23.29%; N, 16.05%. Calc. for $\text{CaN}_2\text{O}_2, 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Ca, 23.26; N, 16.3 per cent). The calcium salt could not be dehydrated.

Results of experiments with (a) nitrites and (b) hyponitrites, carried out in a nitrometer with thiourea-acetic acid by the standard method (Cumming and Kay, "Quantitative Chemical Analysis", 6th Ed., p. 386) showed that while the pure nitrites were accurately estimable, the hyponitrites were not. Sodium hyponitrite had some action on the reagent but calcium hyponitrite had none; the latter merely dissolved out when the reagent was added but no gas was liberated. Partington and Shah (*loc. cit.*, 1931) found no nitrate or nitrite in the residual liquors of the interaction of water on sodium hyponitrite. They also found that HI and starch did not react with hyponitrite instantaneously and ascribed the blue colour which appeared on standing for 2 to 3 minutes to the probable presence of traces of nitrite in their hyponitrite, while Oza (this *Journal*, 1945, 22, 225) considered this phenomenon as a peculiar property of the hyponitrite as nitrites liberated iodine instantaneously even when present in very minute amounts.

Table I contains results of experiments, in the nitrometer, with mixtures of nitrite and hyponitrite, when acted upon by thiourea-acetic acid. The results show that calcium nitrite can be estimated in presence of the hyponitrite by this method. Sodium hyponitrite (soluble) appears therefore to behave exceptionally in having some action on the reagent. If hyponitrite ion has no action on thiourea-acetic acid, as is indicated by the inactivity of the reagent to the calcium salt, the apparent little reactivity of the reagent to the sodium salt may be the result of the production of sodium nitrite, as an intermediate unstable product, in the action of water on sodium hyponitrite. Having noticed that the amounts of nitrite in the aqueous solutions of sodium hyponitrite increased slowly with time, Partington and Shah (*loc. cit.*) became inclined to the view that the nitrite might have resulted from the hyponitrite by the action of water. The action of water is being investigated systematically.

TABLE I

Experiments in a nitrometer with mixtures of nitrite and hyponitrite and thiourea-acetic acid.

No.	Mass		Gas liberated (N. T. P.).	Gas expected from nitrite content (N. T. P.).
	NaNO_2 .	$\text{Na}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$.		
1	0.0606 g.	0.0163 g.	21.65 c.c.	19.7 c.c.
2	0.0587	0.0164	21.4	19.05
3	0.0382	0.0120	14.0	12.4
	$\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_2)_2, \text{H}_2\text{O}$.	$\text{CaN}_2\text{O}_2, 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$.		
4	0.0502	0.0200	14.7	14.9
5	0.0600	0.0150	17.7	17.9

The apparatus used to study the action of water at the b. p. is shown in Fig. 1. It consists of a tube B, to which a side tube C, graduated at its upper end, is attached

•FIG. 1

through a vacuum tap P. The tube B is connected to a bulb A of about 100 c.c. capacity by a ground-in-glass joint through a vacuum tap X. The upper end of the bulb can be closed when required by the tap Y. Through Y, the apparatus led to a P_2O_5 tube closed by another vacuum tap Z and thence to the Hyvac and sprengel pumps. A quantity of hyponitrite is accurately weighed out in B and the apparatus fitted up. P is closed and X, Y and Z are all opened and the system evacuated and tested for leaks by standing overnight. Water is placed in C. X is closed and about 5 c.c. water allowed carefully to enter B and a boiling water-bath placed about the latter. Vigorous reaction occurred with the sodium salt but with the calcium salt considerable period of heating was needed to complete the reaction. To pump off the gaseous products of the reaction, Y and Z were closed and X partially opened, very cautiously, for a moment and closed. Y was then

opened to the P_2O_5 tube and then Z to the sprengel pump and the dry gas pumped off. This was repeated several times till all the gas was pumped off. The residual liquors in B were tested for nitrite and nitrate but none was found; the liquors were strongly alkaline as expected. The gas was analysed for nitric oxide, nitrous oxide and nitrogen. The nitric oxide was absorbed out in alkaline sodium sulphite, previously saturated with nitrous oxide. The nitrous oxide was then absorbed out in cold alcohol till after several bubblings and storage over fresh alcohol for two hours no contraction in volume occurred. The gas left unabsorbed was taken as nitrogen. Table II contains the results, the recorded volumes being at N. T. P. The results show that though the main reaction appears to be

the exact reactions may not be quite so simple. Further, the salts decompose completely.

TABLE II

Products of decomposition of $Na_2N_2O_2$ and $CaN_2O_2, 4H_2O$ in water when boiled in vacuum.

No.	2 Substance.	3 Mass of subs. in column 2	4 Gas obtained (N. T. P.).	5 Compn. of gas in column 4.			6 Vol. of N_2O expected acc. to $RN_2O_2 = RO + N_2O$.
				NO.	N_2O .	N_2 .	
1	$Na_2N_2O_2$	0.0224 g.	4.85 c.c.	0.1	4.6	0.15	4.75
2	"	0.0332	6.95	0.1	6.5	0.35	7.0
3	"	0.0260	5.45	0.15	5.1	0.25	5.5
4	"	0.0250	5.10	0.1	4.8	0.15	5.3
5	$CaN_2O_2, 4H_2O$	0.0750	10.3	0.45	7.55	2.25	9.75
6	"	0.0502	7.3	0.45	5.65	1.20	6.5
7	"	0.0752	10.2	0.55	7.85	1.80	9.8

In view of the above behaviour of sodium hyponitrite, it seemed well worth enquiring into the behaviour of the mixtures of nitrite and hyponitrite of sodium, the latter being admitted to the nitrometer after previously boiling (to decompose) it. Quantities of nitrite and hyponitrite were accurately weighed out, about 3 c.c. of water added and the solution gently boiled for some minutes. The solution was then cooled and transferred to the nitrometer with the usual care. The reagent was added and the nitrometer shaken as usual. Table III gives the results which show that nitrite estimation is now very satisfactory.

TABLE III

Estimation of NaNO_2 in presence of $\text{Na}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$ in a nitrometer, after boiling their aqueous soln.

No.	Mass (NaNO_2).	Mass ($\text{Na}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$).	Gas obtained (N. T. P.).	Gas expected from nitrite content (N. T. P.).
1	0.0249 g.	0.0180 g.	8.2 c.c.	8.1 c.c.
2	0.0292	0.0224	9.3	9.5
3	0.0349	0.0120	11.4	11.3
4	0.0406	0.0332	13.2	13.2
5	0.0459	0.0288	14.7	14.9
6	0.0550	0.0432	17.7	17.85

TABLE IV

Estimation of nitrite in presence of hyponitrite, after boiling, by the permanganate method.

(Expts. No. 1 to 5 are with sodium, and No. 6 to 10 with calcium salts).

No.	Wt. of nitrite.	Wt. of hyponitrite.	Wt. of nitrite found.	No.	Wt. of nitrite.	Wt. of hyponitrite.	Wt. of nitrite found.
1	0.0398 g.	0.0382 g.	0.03927 g.	6	0.0226 g.	0.0104 g.	0.0223 g.
2	0.0519	0.0356	0.05125	7	0.0276	0.0300	0.0277
3	0.0469	0.0288	0.04604	8	0.0456	0.0400	0.0457
4	0.0259	0.0246	0.0265	9	0.0500	0.0500	0.0488
5	0.0313	0.0144	0.0308	10	0.0756	0.0607	0.0750

Table IV gives the results of estimation of nitrite in its admixture with sodium hyponitrite (soluble hyponitrite) and calcium hyponitrite (insoluble hyponitrite), by the permanganate method. The standard permanganate was added to the solution (or suspension) of the salts after boiling the latter. To accurately weighed quantities of the salts water was added, and the mixture boiled well. To the cooled solution a known excess of standard KMnO_4 was then added and acidified with dilute H_2SO_4 . The whole was heated to 60° in a water-bath, decolorised by adding K-tetroxalate (standard) and the excess of the latter was titrated back. The results show that the method is quite satisfactory.